

Spatial Regression Analysis Using Poisson Regression: Applications in Studying Traffic Accidents

Jaufar Mousa Mohammed

Department of Statistics Sciences, College of Administration & Economic,
Kirkuk University, Iraq

Article History:

Received: 28.04.2025 Revised: 28.05.2025 Accepted: 31.05.2025 Published: 02.06.2025

ABSTRACT:

The study of spatial data and the application to the Poisson regression model, with special interest for the study of traffic accidents, is the objective of this work. Traffic accidents are a pressing problem with wide impacts on urban and road safety. As a result, knowing the pattern of these accidents is essential to urban planning and the development of effective safety measures. This study focuses on the computation of the Poisson regression model and the interpretation of traffic accident data as a dependent variable. It is assumed in this model that accidents happen at random but not independently and they depend on factors (explanatory variables) such as type of road, driver characteristics, character of road vehicle pedestrian other, etc., related to the probability that an accident occurs. Because of its characteristics for spatial data with count dependent variables, Poisson regression has the capability to establish a good model to predict the number of accidents under specific local conditions. The publication reports real-life applications, using traffic accident data collected in certain regions, for example, the spatial analysis which was performed to identify traffic accident hotspots for the 15 governorates of Iraq for the year 2023, and recommendations to improve road safety. The study also shows that the application of Poisson analysis may be an effective approach when strategic decisions are to be made in order to decrease accidents and improve security on the road. Finally, the study demonstrates that researchers should adopt state-of-the-art statistical tools when analyzing spatial information (e.g., Poisson regression), in the service of better practice and scientific solutions aimed at cutting traffic risk at high levels.

Keywords: Poisson Distribution, Poisson Spatial Regression, Poisson Regression.

Suggested Citation: J.M. Mohammed, " Spatial Regression Analysis Using Poisson Regression: Applications in Studying Traffic Accidents," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 3(3), pp. 268-275, May-Jun 2025. DOI: 10.59324/ejaset.2025.3(3).18

INTRODUCTION

Poisson spatial regression is also among these latest statistics techniques that are employed for the analysis of data in which the counts of events or accidents take place at different geographical locations or periods of time. This model is derived from the Poisson distribution, which is a probability distribution used to express the number of events that occur in a fixed timeframe or spatial region. Such events could be accidents in traffic, crimes, infectious diseases, or generally any event that is specified through counting. In practice these data can be highly dependent and not fully independent, for example due to spatial location, or separation by time or environment. As such, models taking into account the spatial influence on the occurrences need to be used when working with such data.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

This issue can be dealt with spatial Poisson regression which combines Poisson's model with spatial features which estimate the relationship of different events in different locations of the spatially variable.

The principal lines of applications of this model cover areas as diverse as urban planning (in order to analyze the behavior of traffic accidents within cities), or public health (to study the propagation of epidemic diseases over the geographical nests). It is also applied in economics for the analysis of spatial economic phenomena, such as the distribution of investment or unemployment. In this paper we discuss background theory regarding spatial Poisson regression model and its application in representation of traffic accidents using Poisson probability distribution and spatial effects to enhance prediction. We will also discuss some applications of this model in the analysis of spatial data, and practical difficulties and limitations that a researcher might face in using it. The study of these models has deep connections with spatial behavior of the original system and can provide effective approach to complex problems that need to explore spatial response of multiple factors. Future work in developing this model and its application in various areas will be discussed in the last section of this paper [4].

Research Objective

The objective of this study is to apply the Poisson regression model to assess road traffic accidents (RTA) spatial data in Iraq on some explanatory variables. The objective of such studies is to identify the variables related to the distribution of accidents, identify hot-spots, and recommend better road safety.

POISSON DISTRIBUTION

The Poisson distribution is a probability distribution used in cases where an event takes place without warning in a continuum of time or space. In other words, it refers to the events that can happen in a fixed time span or a fixed area. The rate μ of these events that actually occurs is given by the parameter λ , representing the average or expected number of events. The Poisson distribution is given by:

$$P(Y = y) = \frac{\lambda^y e^{-\lambda}}{y!} \quad (1)$$

Y is the number of events, λ is the occurrence rate (or the expected rate of events), and e is the natural logarithm [6].

Traditional Poisson Regression

Count model regression, or Poisson regression [2] is a special case of Generalized Linear Models (GLM) in which we have count response data. This model is especially appropriate when the dependent variable (i.e., the one that we want to predict) tends to be quantity of events or accidents, and these ones fit to a Poisson distribution. On the other hand, the model serves as an analogy to a number of independent variables, population density, environmental level, etc., which can possibly affect the event frequency. Therefore, the relationship between the dependent variable Y (the number of events) and the independent variables is expressed using the natural logarithm of the occurrence rate λ , such that:

$$\ln(\lambda) = X_1\beta_1 + X_2\beta_2 + \dots + X_n\beta_n + e \quad (2)$$

Where λ is the expected rate of occurrences (the number of events), X is the vector of independent variables, β is the vector of coefficients representing the effect of each independent variable on λ ,

$\ln(\lambda)$ is the natural logarithm of the rate, ensuring that λ remains a positive value, and e represents random errors [7,8].

Poisson Spatial Regression Model with Spatial Lag

When spatial effects are incorporated into the model, we obtain spatial Poisson regression. In this model, spatial effects on traffic accidents are considered by adding the spatial correlation between different locations, reflecting the impact of neighboring locations. The spatial model can be expressed as follows

$$\ln(\lambda_i) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{1i} + \beta_2 X_{2i} + \dots + \rho(WY)_i + e$$

In this model (3), the spatial effect $\rho(WY)_i$ is added for each location, which is a random variable dependent on the spatial correlation between locations. The spatial effect is typically represented using a weight matrix that describes how location i influences its neighboring locations. This effect captures unobservable influences such as local spatial factors. ρ is a coefficient that reflects the strength of the spatial effect [3,6].

Maximum Likelihood in Poisson Regression with Spatial Lag

To calculate the joint likelihood function for all locations in the Poisson model, the joint probability for all locations is the product of the individual probabilities for each location:

$$L(\beta, \rho) = \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{\lambda_i^{Y_i} e^{-\lambda_i}}{Y_i!} \quad (4)$$

$$\Rightarrow \ln L(\beta, \rho) = \sum_{i=1}^n [Y_i \ln(\lambda_i) - \lambda_i - \ln(Y_i!)]$$

$$\ln(\lambda_i) = X_i \beta + \rho(WY)_i + e$$

$$\ln L(\beta, \rho) = \sum_{i=1}^n [Y_i (X_i \beta + \rho(WY)_i) - \exp(X_i \beta + \rho(WY)_i) - \ln(Y_i!)] \quad (5)$$

Due to the non-linear nature of the equation, it is often not possible to solve it analytically. Therefore, numerical optimization techniques are used, such as the Newton-Raphson algorithm, to find the values of β and ρ that maximize the log-likelihood function [5].

Spatial Weights Matrix

It is a square matrix ($n \times n$) with positive values, and it does not necessarily need to be symmetric. It is constructed based on the proximity or adjacency between observations, meaning the neighboring relationships for each location are represented in one row of the matrix. The diagonal elements of the matrix are set to zero. The choice of the spatial weight matrix plays a crucial role in determining the spatial effects, as it defines the strength and nature of spatial dependence between locations. Therefore, an appropriate weight matrix must be constructed.

Binary Contiguity Weights Matrix

It is a square matrix ($n \times n$) defined such that if i and j are adjacent, then $w_{ij} = 1$ and if i and j are not adjacent, then $w_{ij} = 0$, as shown in the following formula:

$$W = (w_{ij})_{n \times n} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i \text{ neighbor } j \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Row - Standardized Weights Matrix

This matrix is called the modified matrix, and its rows sum to one. It is based on the computation of the matrix of weights associated with pairwise adjacencies, defined by the following equation [2]:

$$W^{\text{std}} = (w_{ij}) = \begin{cases} \frac{w_{ij}}{\sum_i w_{ij}} & \text{if } i \text{ neighbor } j \quad 0 < W^{\text{std}} \leq 1 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Moran Test

The measure is based on the mathematical model $Y = X\beta + E$, the same is measured by Moran's I coefficient. If the difference of values at two consecutive locations is lower than the difference of values at far apart locations it reflects a local homogeneity. For example, if the value of a variable at one location is value at the adjacent location for the same variable, then we say there is spatial autocorrelation of variables. Moran's I coefficient is one of the fundamental methods for measuring spatial autocorrelation relationship among components of research phenomenon and identifying its spatial pattern i.e. dispersed (remote), clustered (proximate) or random. It can have values between -1 and +1. Generally, the Moran's I coefficient measures the spatial autocorrelation between locations of spatial elements, and the closer its value is to one, the stronger the spatial autocorrelation. The general formula for Moran's I is as follows:

$$I = \frac{n(e'We)}{S_0(e'e)} \quad (8)$$

Where

$S_0 = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij}$ The sum of all the elements of the Weights Matrix W , n is Sample size, e is $(n \times 1)$ vector of random errors.

When using a standardized weight matrix in which the sum of each row is equal to one, in this case, $(n = S_0)$, this equality leads to the simplification of the formula (8) above.

$$I = \frac{(e'we)}{(e'e)} \quad (9)$$

To determine whether the value of the Moran's I coefficient is statistically significant at a certain confidence level, the Moran's Z test is used as shown below, according to the following hypotheses.

$H_0: \rho = 0$, *There is no spatial dependence*

$H_1: \rho \neq 0$, *There is spatial dependence*

$$Z = \frac{I - E(I)}{\sqrt{V(I)}} \quad (10)$$

$$E(I) = \frac{n(\text{tr}(MW))}{S_0(n - k)}$$

$$V(I) = \frac{\text{tr}(MWMW') + (\text{tr}(MW))^2 + (\text{tr}(MW))^2}{(n - k)(n - k + 1)} \left(\frac{n}{S_0}\right)^2 - (E(I))^2$$

Where

$M = I - X(X'X)^{-1}X'$ Symmetric square matrix, tr The sum of the elements of the main diagonal, k is The number of independent variables.

The calculated Z value is compared with the tabulated Z value at a significance level of $(\alpha/2)$. When the Moran's test result is significant, it indicates the presence of spatial dependence between geographic regions, which requires spatial analysis using spatial regression models. Otherwise, the general linear regression model (GLM) is sufficient [1].

APPLICATION

This study includes 15 governorates (locations) regarding the number of traffic accidents in various governorates of Iraq for the year 2023. The data was collected from the source of the Directorate of Transport and Communications Statistics for the year 2024. Here, (Y) represents the total number of accidents, which is the dependent variable, while the independent variables are: X_1 the number of accidents caused by the road, X_2 the number of accidents caused by the vehicle, X_3 the number of accidents caused by the driver, and X_4 accidents caused by pedestrians. Each location has coordinates $u(x)$ (indicating east-west) and $v(x)$ (indicating north-south), as shown in Table 1. It is assumed that this spatial data follows a Poisson distribution.

Table 1. Statistics on the Number of Traffic Accidents in Iraq for the Year 2023

Governorates	Y	X_1	X_2	X_3	X_4	$u(x)$	$v(x)$
Nineveh	475	60	81	286	48	30	62
Kirkuk	364	10	25	309	20	38	54
Diyala	1086	0	1086	0	0	40	40
Anbar	455	9	18	411	17	30	38
Baghdad	1474	186	525	703	60	39	39
Babylon	1043	31	53	907	52	37	28
Karbala	618	23	9	550	36	35	30
Wasit	1129	186	270	512	161	48	30
Salahuddin	347	51	55	214	27	33	47
Najaf	858	4	8	846	0	36	25
AL-Qadisiyah	728	1	5	720	2	42	27
Muthanna	355	3	31	321	0	43	20
Dhi Qar	531	4	10	507	10	50	20
Maysan	287	1	0	285	1	55	25
Basra	1667	81	114	1472	0	60	15

Moran's I Test

The Moran's I index value and its associated Z value were calculated to analyze the spatial pattern of the data. The results indicate that the I value of 0.1709 reflects a weak positive spatial autocorrelation, meaning there is a slight tendency for similar values to cluster geographically. However, the Z value of 1.3610 shows that this correlation is not statistically significant, suggesting that this pattern may be the result of chance.

Table 2. Moran's I Index Result

I	$Z(I)$
0.1709	1.3610

Estimation of Parameters

The parameters of the spatial Poisson regression model with spatial effects were estimated using formula (5), and the following results were obtained.

Table 3. Results of Poisson Regression Coefficients Estimation

β_0	β_1	β_2	β_3	β_4	ρ
0.5005	0.0108	0.0115	0.0264	0.0101	0.0503

$$\begin{aligned} \ln(\lambda_i) = & 0.5005 + 0.0108X_1 + 0.0115X_2 + 0.0264\beta_3 + 0.0101\beta_4 \\ & + 0.0503(WY) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

From this formula (11), the values of Y , which follow a Poisson distribution for both the conventional case and with the spatial effect WY , were estimated. The results are shown in Table 4 below.

Table 4. Results of Estimated Values

Traditional Poisson	Poisson with Spatial lag $\rho(WY)$
10.1147	30.285
9.2551	26.709
12.989	63.2
11.8263	52.192
27.7115	68.555
25.9143	71.529
15.7355	55.237
20.7567	63.922
7.6056	46.376
22.9696	55.151
19.5965	58.991
9.3633	56.947
14.144	56.053
8.0449	63.827
41.5466	61.213

CONCLUSIONS

The parameter $\beta_0 = 0.5005$ is the constant term in the model and represents the log-average value of the dependent variable (such as the number of events or frequencies) when all independent variables are equal to zero. In the context of spatial data, this indicates the baseline number of events at a geographic location without the influence of other factors. The positive value 0.5005 means that there is a positive baseline rate of events even in the absence of variables.

The coefficient $\beta_1 = 0.0108$ represents the effect of the first independent variable in the Poisson model. Coefficients are interpreted in terms of log rates. A value of 0.0108 means that with each one-unit increase in the first independent variable, the natural logarithm of the average number of events increases by 1.0109. When converted to a percentage change (Exponential), we get $e^{0.0108} = 1.0109$.

The coefficient $\beta_2 = 0.0115$ represents the effect of the second independent variable on the dependent variable. A value of 0.0115 means that a one-unit increase in this variable leads to an increase in the natural logarithm of the average number of events by 1.0116. When converted to a percentage change: $e^{0.0115} = 1.0116$.

The coefficient $\beta_3 = 0.0264$ represents the effect of the third independent variable. A one-unit increase in this variable leads to an increase in the natural logarithm of the average number of events by 1.0268. When converted to a percentage change: $e^{(0.0264)} = 1.0268$.

The coefficient $\beta_4 = 0.0101$ represents the effect of the fourth independent variable. A one-unit increase in this variable leads to an increase in the natural logarithm of the average number of events by 1.0102. When converted to a percentage change: $e^{(0.0101)} = 1.0102$.

The spatial effect coefficient (ρ) = 0.0503 reflects the strength of spatial autocorrelation between geographical locations. It is a positive value between (0, 1), indicating a relatively acceptable spatial dependence. This means that the number of events at a given location is influenced by the number of events at neighboring locations. The closer the value is to 1, the more spatial similarity there is between locations, suggesting that neighboring locations share similar conditions or patterns.

In general, all independent variables (road, vehicle, driver, and pedestrians) have a positive effect on the number of accidents. The highest relative effect was for the driver ($\beta_3 = 0.0264$), suggesting that the driver's behavior plays a significant role in accidents, while the effects of pedestrians, vehicles, and roads were relatively lower.

In Table 4, the predicted values show that the Poisson model with the spatial effect yields significantly larger values than the traditional model. This indicates that the traditional model may suffer from underestimation due to neglecting spatial dependence.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Poisson distribution can be used in spatial distributions and spatial regression to make future predictions.
2. Use data that follows a Poisson distribution for more accurate modeling and analysis.
3. The Poisson model with spatial effects should be relied upon when studying traffic accidents to avoid underestimating the number of accidents in areas with high spatial dependence.
4. Since the driver is the most influential variable, enhancing driver training programs and ensuring adherence to traffic laws can reduce accidents.
5. Investing in road infrastructure improvement and minimizing interaction with pedestrian traffic can reduce the likelihood of accidents.
6. Analyzing data across different time periods (such as seasons or peak hours) may reveal additional spatial and temporal patterns.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. B. Omar, "Application of Spatial Error Model for Ordinary and Fuzzy Data with Comparison," *Journal of Positive Sciences*, vol. 21, 2023.
- [2] D. B. Omar and A. F. Tawfeeq, "Estimating Parameters of Some Spatial Regression Models with Experimental and Applied Study," *Journal of Positive Sciences*, vol. 17, no. 2, pp. 2095–2107, 2020.
- [3] E. L. Frome, "The Analysis of Rates Using Poisson Regression Models," *Biometrics*, vol. 39, no. 3, pp. 665–674, 1983.
- [4] J. M. Mohammed, "Technique Kriging Estimation in Geostatistics with Application," *University of Kirkuk Journal for Administrative and Economic Sciences*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 220–236, 2015.
- [5] R. Sellner, M. M. Fischer, and M. Koch, "A Spatial Autoregressive Poisson Gravity Model," *Geographical Analysis*, vol. 45, no. 2, pp. 180–201, 2013. doi: 10.1111/gean.12007
- [6] T. E. Smith, *Spatial Data Analysis*, University of Pennsylvania, School of Engineering and Applied Science. [Online]. Available: <https://www.seas.upenn.edu/~tesmith/>

- [7] S. W. Tyas and L. A. Puspitasari, "Geographically Weighted Generalized Poisson Regression Model with the Best Kernel Function in the Case of the Number of Postpartum Maternal Mortality in East Java," *MethodsX*, vol. 10, p. 102002, 2023. doi: 10.1016/j.mex.2023.102002
- [8] S. Yang and G. Berdine, "Poisson Regression," *The Southwest Respiratory and Critical Care Chronicles*, vol. 3, no. 9, pp. 61–64, 2015.

